

Model of Character Building for Elementary School Students

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Abstract

This research has the intention of proposing a character-building model for elementary school students. This model can improve character building by promoting character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement. The sample group of 450 students represented grades 4-6 from 5 elementary schools in Jakarta. The students were asked in the questionnaires to provide samples of character building conducted in their school in the context of character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement. The data in this research were analysed using the structural equation model (SEM). On the basis of the statistical analyses, the research finding was that character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement had predictive effects on character building. This study makes a practical contribution by showing that character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement enhancing character building to improve the level of student attitude by supplying a model for character building. Applying this model, the students' noble character can be improved leading to virtuous society.

Keywords: Character building; teaching learning process; extracurricular activities; school culture; community involvement

1. Introduction

Elementary schools in Indonesia mainly provide the priority on the cognitive aspect of education. Jakarta being the capital city of Indonesia is very critical regarding to diminishing student characters. Primary school age is a critical age to shape personality.

Character education was applied through culture, rules, regulations, events and ceremonies leading to shape good habits for students (Izfanna and Hisyam, 2012). Integration of character values was implemented in courses, such as Classroom Discipline. Positive characters of the students can be developed through the educational process. Character education was very critical in teacher preparation during the accreditation process (Jones, Ryan, & Bohlin, 2012). However, most research only focused on general aspects of character building.

The data of the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture on 10 May 2018 showed that 148,856 elementary schools, 1,480,710 teachers, 25,395,436 students, 117,314 educational staff, and 1,114,408 learning groups were present in Indonesia. There were 1,537 state and 914 private elementary schools, 10,747 male and 27,903 female teachers, 420,539 male and 392,327 female students, 2,130 male and 1,536 female educational staff, and 29,116 learning groups in Jakarta. There were 176 state and 197 private elementary schools in the north Jakarta region, 352 state and 179 private

elementary schools in the south Jakarta region, 445 state and 197 private elementary schools in the east Jakarta region, 360 state and 241 private elementary schools in the west Jakarta region, and 190 state and 100 private elementary schools in the central Jakarta region.

National accreditation is an indicator used to determine the quality of elementary schools in Indonesia. Based on National Ministry of Education Regulation No. 11 (2009), the accreditation level of elementary schools is related to eight standards (content, process, graduate competency, educator and educational staff, infrastructure, management, financing, and evaluation standards). However, evaluation of school quality leading to the accreditation level is not optimal, because elementary school evaluation largely based upon reported documents. In fact, character building has not been integrated optimally at elementary schools in Jakarta.

This study was conducted at 5 different elementary schools in the north, south, central, west, and east Jakarta regions consisting of Kelapa Gading Timur 03, Tebet Timur 15 Pagi, Muhammadiyah 24, Pinangsia 06 Pagi, and Karisma Islamic elementary schools. The accreditation of the Kelapa Gading Timur 03 is excellent, whereas Tebet Timur 15 Pagi, Muhammadiyah 24, Pinangsia 06 Pagi, and Karisma Islamic elementary school has not been accredited.

2. Literature review

Character education at schools conducted thematic approach through storytelling, discussion, group work, and other aspects of school activities (Revell, 2002). Character education was only implemented in specific activities. Fahmy, Bachtiar, Rahim and Malik (2015) stated that character education happened through attitudes and behaviors concerning to be obedient to the teachings of one's religion, tolerant of others, and live harmoniously with other religions. Marini (2017) found that character values integrated in religious school culture related to facilities and opportunities for worship, praying together, religious mottos and songs displayed at the school, religious activities, such as slaughtering qurban on Idul Adha day, the drive of infaq culture to give money to destitute people, wearing Moslem uniforms every Friday, and the inclusion of religious boarding schools to improve religious faith, morals, and worship.

A study conducted by Izfanna & Hisyam (2012) found that the method used to carry out character education at Pondok Pesantren Darunnajah was depended on knowledge, conditional methods, and practices applied through the formal subjects of *akhlaq* content, Islamic theology, Qur'an, Hadith, Fiqh, Mahfuzhat, Muthala'ah, and Ushuluddin related to good characters. Character building was implemented through Ibadah practices or the practical duties of Islam.

Jones, Ryan, and Bohlin (2012) confirmed that character building was not existed in the teacher education curriculum. However, Meidl & Meidl (2013) found that character building was stated in the curricula and part of the school mission statements realized in school culture. Cubukcu (2012) established that hidden curricula integrated in social and cultural activities developed the character education process, especially for interpersonal communication quality among students.

Furkan (2014) provided that character building was conducted in activities of caring, cleanliness, beauty and tidiness, religious service obedience, conformity to the rules, mutual respect, politeness, family-like relationships, honesty and responsibility, togetherness, tidy document filing and educational infrastructure, and stakeholders' participation and involvement. Oktarina, Widiyanto, and Soekardi (2015) suggested that character building was conducted in classroom, school culture, and extracurricular activities including Scouting.

The hypotheses tested are in the following:

- H1. Character building in teaching learning process has positive association with character building

- H2.* Character building in extracurricular activities has positive association with character building
- H3.* Character building in school culture has positive association with character building
- H4.* Character building through community involvement has positive association with character building
- H5.* The teacher returning the homework evaluated on time is positively connected with character building in teaching learning process
- H6.* The teacher giving same opportunities to all students to get the best score is positively connected with character building in teaching learning process
- H7.* The teacher being responsible for finishing assignment is positively connected with character building in teaching learning process
- H8.* Extracurricular activities being able to improve student teamwork competences is positively connected with character building in extracurricular activities
- H9.* Extracurricular activities being able to improve student school motivation is positively connected with character building in extracurricular activities
- H10.* Extracurricular activities being able to improve student leadership competences is positively connected with character building in extracurricular activities
- H11.* The student feeling secure at school is positively connected with character building in school culture
- H12.* Principal, teachers, parents, and community supporting the students is positively connected with character building in school culture
- H13.* School giving security physically is positively connected with character building in school culture
- H14.* The school inviting public figure to give religious lecture is positively connected with character building through community involvement
- H15.* Cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school is positively connected with character building through community involvement
- H16.* Community participating in preventing dengue fever outbreak is positively connected with character building through community involvement

Theoretical framework

This study hypothesizes that character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement promote character building at elementary school. Indicators of the teacher returns the homework evaluated on time, the teacher gives same opportunities to all students to get the best score, and the teacher is responsible for finishing assignment will estimate the effectiveness of character building in teaching learning process (Cubukcu, 2012). The quality of character building in extracurricular activities will be predicted by indicators of extracurricular activities can improve student teamwork competences, extracurricular activities can improve student school motivation, and extracurricular activities can improve student leadership competences (Marini, 2017). Effectiveness of character building in school culture is promoted by indicators of the student feel secure at school, principal, teachers, parents, and community support the students, and school gives security physically (Marini, Safitri, & Muda, 2018). Character building through community involvement is estimated by indicators of the school invites public figure to give religious lecture, cooperation between elementary school and community maintains cleanliness the environment surrounding school, and community participates in preventing dengue fever outbreak (Wahyudi, Zulela., Marini, Marzuki, Barokah,

&Mahmudi, 2019; Wahyudi, Zulela, Marini, Choirudin, Ayshwarya, Nguyen, Shankar, 2019). Figure 1 shows the theoretical framework of this study.

3. Research design

A survey using questionnaires was conducted in collecting data related to character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement. A total of 450 students from 5 different elementary schools in north, south, central, west, and east Jakarta in DKI Jakarta province replied the survey.

Content analysis of the literature for character building was conducted on the basis of Marini, Safitri, & Muda (2018); Oktarina, Widiyanto, and Soekardi (2015); Furkan, (2014); Izfanna, D. and Hisyam, M. A. (2012); Wahyudi, Zulela, Marini, Marzuki, Barokah, & Mahmudi (2019); Wahyudi, Zulela, Marini, Choirudin, Ayshwarya, Nguyen, Shankar, (2019) which consisted of four aspects as follows: character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement. These ideals were converted into statements in the questionnaire.

The questions regarding character building consisted of four dimensions: character building in teaching learning process, in extracurricular activities, in school culture, and through community involvement. Character building in teaching learning process consists of three indicators (the teacher returns the homework evaluated on time, the teacher gives same opportunities to all students to get the best score, and the teacher is responsible for finishing assignment). Character building in extracurricular activities consists of three indicators (extracurricular activities can improve student teamwork competences, extracurricular activities can improve student school motivation, and extracurricular activities can improve student leadership competences). Character building in school culture consists of three indicators (the student feel secure at school, principal, teachers, parents, and community support the students, and school gives security physically). Character building through community involvement consists of three indicators (the school invites public figure to give religious lecture, cooperation between elementary school and community maintains cleanliness the environment surrounding school, and community participates in preventing dengue fever outbreak). The summary of relationships hypothesized is represented in a model shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework of the study

The structural equation model (SEM) analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics 24 and SPSS AMOS 24 with 2017 Edition was used to examine the set of relationships between character building in religious school culture as the exogenous variable and student religious character as the endogenous variable. Data input was performed using Excel by entering the scores of each item based on the responses of the 450 participants with “strongly agree”, “agree”, “neutral”, “disagree”, and “strongly disagree”(scored 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively, for positive questions and 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively, for negative questions).

Findings

The goodness-of-fit statistical analysis results can be seen in Table I. These findings showed that Normed Fit Index (NFI) value attained 0.663 showing that the model proposed is good fit. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value arrived at 0.695 demonstrating that the model recommended is good fit. Incremental Fit Index (IFI) value attained 0.700 showing that the model is good fit. Relative Fit Index (RFI) value gained 0.555 indicating that the model submitted is good fit. Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) value got to 0.901 presenting that the model is good fit. Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) value reached 0.845 showing that the model hypothesized is good fit. SEM measurement displaying that model promoted in this study is a fit model.

Table I. Model Fit Summary

Fit measurement	Fit Value		
	<i>Cut-Off Limitation</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
NFI	$0 < \text{NFI} < 1; \text{NFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.663	Good Fit
CFI	$0 < \text{CFI} < 1; \text{CFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.695	Good Fit
IFI	$0 < \text{IFI} < 1; \text{IFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.700	Good Fit
RFI	$0 < \text{RFI} < 1; \text{RFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.555	Good Fit
GFI	$0 < \text{GFI} < 1; \text{GFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.901	Good Fit
AGFI	$0 < \text{AGFI} < 1; \text{AGFI} \geq 0.90 = \text{good fit}$	0.845	Good Fit

A measurement model test of the observed variables is exposed in Table II. Table II displayed that the correlation coefficients between character building in teaching learning process, character building in extracurricular activities, and character building through community involvement with character building were 0.850, 0.570, and 0.529, respectively, which were significant at the 0.05 level according to the *t* statistics. However, the correlation coefficients between character building in school culture with character building reaching 0.997 was not supported. The observed variables the teacher giving same opportunities to all students to get the best score and the teacher being responsible for finishing assignment had significant correlation coefficients with character building in teaching learning process of 0.455 and 0.101, respectively. However, the correlation between the teacher returning the homework evaluated on time and character building in teaching learning process of 0.417 was not supported in this research. The observed variables extracurricular activities being able to improve student teamwork competences, extracurricular activities being able to improve student school motivation, and extracurricular activities being able to improve student leadership competences with character building in extracurricular activities had significant coefficients of 0.672, 0.725, and 0.540, respectively. The observed variables School giving security physically had significant association with character building in school culture of 0.672. However, association between the student feeling secure at school and principal, teachers, parents, and community supporting the students with character building in school culture of 0.506 and 0.524, respectively were not supported. The observed variable the school inviting

public figure to give religious lecture, cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school, and community participating in preventing dengue fever outbreak with character building through community involvement had significant coefficients of 0.681, 0.547, and 0.668, respectively. However, association between the school inviting public figure to give religious lecture and Cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school with character building through community involvement of 0.668 and 0.547, respectively, were not supported. The structural model is shown in Figure 2.

Table II. Measurement model test (Regression Weights: Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TEACH	<---	CHAR	0.761	0.174	4.381	***	
EXCUL	<---	CHAR	0.798	0.164	4.875	***	
CULT	<---	CHAR	0.264	0.246	1.071	0.284	Not Valid
COMM	<---	CHAR	1.000				
CB3	<---	TEACH	1.000				
CB2	<---	TEACH	1.137	0.247	4.603	***	
CB1	<---	TEACH	0.451	0.296	1.524	0.127	Not Valid
CB6	<---	EXCUL	1.000				
CB5	<---	EXCUL	1.318	0.145	9.071	***	
CB4	<---	EXCUL	0.899	0.107	8.428	***	
CB9	<---	CULT	1.000				
CB8	<---	CULT	5.834	5.384	1.084	0.279	Not Valid
CB7	<---	CULT	4.472	4.129	1.083	0.279	Not Valid
CB12	<---	COMM	1.000				
CB11	<---	COMM	0.861	0.107	8.061	***	
CB10	<---	COMM	0.938	0.111	8.450	***	

Source: AMOS Results 2019

Table II. Measurement model test (Standardized Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
TEACH	<---	CHAR	0.850
EXCUL	<---	CHAR	0.570
CULT	<---	CHAR	0.997
COMM	<---	CHAR	0.529
CB3	<---	TEACH	0.417
CB2	<---	TEACH	0.455
CB1	<---	TEACH	0.101
CB6	<---	EXCUL	0.672
CB5	<---	EXCUL	0.725
CB4	<---	EXCUL	0.540
CB9	<---	CULT	0.066
CB8	<---	CULT	0.524
CB7	<---	CULT	0.506
CB12	<---	COMM	0.668
CB11	<---	COMM	0.547

CB10	<---	COMM	Estimate
			0.681

Source: AMOS Results 2019

Notes:

- CHAR = character building
- TEACH = character building in teaching learning process
- EXCUL = character building in extracurricular activities
- CULT = character building in school culture
- COMM = character building through community involvement
- CB1 = the teacher returns the homework evaluated on time
- CB2 = the teacher gives same opportunities to all students to get the best score
- CB3 = the teacher is responsible for finishing assignment
- CB4 = extracurricular activities can improve student teamwork competences
- CB5 = extracurricular activities can improve student school motivation
- CB6 = extracurricular activities can improve student leadership competences
- CB7 = the student feel secure at school
- CB8 = principal, teachers, parents, and community support the students
- CB9 = school gives security physically
- CB10 = the school invites public figure to give religious lecture
- CB11 = cooperation between elementary school and community maintains cleanliness the environment surrounding school
- CB12 = community participates in preventing dengue fever outbreak

Figure 2. The structural model

Discussions

Table I shows that the NFI value attained 0.663, which was more than 0 and less than 1 presenting that the model proposed was already fit. Table 1 showed that the CFI value came to 0.695, which was a value more than 0 and less than 1 and demonstrating that the model was fit. The IFI value reached 0.700, which was more than 0 and less than 1 showing that the model proposed was already fit. The RFI value reached 0.555, which was more than 0 and less than 1 showing that the model suggested was already fit. The GFI was 0.901, which was greater than 0.9 demonstrating that the recommended model was already fit. The AGFI was 0.845, which was more than 0 and less than 1 showing that the hypothesized model was a good fit for the data.

Table II found that character building in teaching learning process, character building in extracurricular activities, and character building through community involvement were positively correlated with character building as exogenous variables with coefficients of 0.850, 0.570, and 0.529, respectively, which were significant at the 0.05 level according to the *t* statistics. Similarly, Marini (2017) stated that extracurricular activity was one of character building program conducted at elementary schools to improve the student characters. However, the association between character building in school culture with character building reaching 0.997 were not supported in this research. This finding is not similar to the finding of the study of Marini, Safitri, Muda (2018); Izfanna & Hisyam (2012); Meidl & Meidl (2013); Furkan (2014); Marini (2017) concluding that character education was done through religious school culture determined by worship facilities, religious ceremonies, and religious symbols.

The teacher giving same opportunities to all students to get the best score and the teacher being responsible for finishing assignment had significant association with character building in teaching learning process of 0.455 and 0.101, respectively. This finding is similar to the finding of the study of Fahmy, Bachtiar, Rahim, and Malik (2015) and Cubukcu (2012), stating that character education was carried out through intracurricular activities. However, association between the teacher returning the homework evaluated on time and character building in teaching learning process of 0.417 was not supported in this research.

Correlation between extracurricular activities being able to improve student teamwork competences, extracurricular activities being able to improve student school motivation, and extracurricular activities being able to improve student leadership competences with character building in extracurricular activities had significant coefficients of 0.672, 0.725, and 0.540, respectively. Similarly, Marini (2017) stated that extracurricular activities integrated with character values can improve student characters.

School giving security physically had significantly associated with character building in school culture of 0.672. However, correlation between the student feeling secure at school and principal, teachers, parents, and community supporting the students with character building in school culture of 0.506 and 0.524, respectively were not supported. In line with the study of Marini, Safitri, & Muda (2018) and Izfanna & Hisyam (2012), religious school culture conducted promoted the student religious characters.

Association between communities participating in preventing dengue fever outbreak with character building through community involvement had significant coefficients of 0.681. However, correlation between the school inviting public figure to give religious lecture and Cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school with character building through community involvement of 0.668 and 0.547, respectively, were not supported. This finding is similar to that of the study of Marini, Safitri, & Muda (2018), which claimed that character building in teaching learning process, extracurricular activities, and character building through community involvement promoted character. However, according to the study of Marini, Safitri, & Muda (2018), association between character building in school culture with character building was supported.

4. Conclusion

Character Building as an empirical model is proposed by this research. Character building in teaching learning process, character building in extracurricular activities, and character building through community involvement can encourage character building. However, character building cannot be supported by character building in school culture. The teacher giving same opportunities to all students to get the best score and the teacher being responsible for finishing assignment promote character building in teaching learning. However, the teacher returning the homework evaluated on time cannot predict character building in teaching learning process. Extracurricular activities being able to improve student teamwork competences, extracurricular activities being able to improve student school motivation, and extracurricular activities being able to improve student leadership competences promote character building in extracurricular activities. School giving security physically estimates character building in school culture. However, the student feeling secure at school and principal, teachers, parents, and community supporting the students cannot support character buildings in school culture. The school inviting public figure to give religious lecture, cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school, and community participating in preventing dengue fever outbreak encourage character building through community involvement. However, the school inviting public figure to give religious lecture and Cooperation between elementary school and community maintaining cleanliness the environment surrounding school cannot predict character building through community involvement.

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